

National Virtual Conference on “Recovery Strategies of Aviation, Hospitality & Tourism Industry post Covid-19”

STUDENTS AND TEACHERS’ INSIGHTS ABOUT ONLINE CLASSES DURING COVID-19

Harinakshi

Research Scholar, Institute of Management & Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka, India. Email: harinakshisuvarna02@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The world is fighting COVID-19 and a lockdown has been announced by economies around the world. Work from Home (WFH) has become the norm, particularly for service organizations. According to Government instructions, even the educational institutions had to close down momentarily, impacting the academic delivery. Therefore, education institutions needed to consider new approaches to the teaching process, and the way was virtual teaching. This study was undertaken to know the effect of lockdown on the teaching-learning process primarily to evaluate the different benefits, challenges faced by teachers and students during online classes. Network issues, lack of training and lack of awareness have been stated as the major challenges they face. The major limitations of virtual classes were found to be less attendance, lack of personal touch and lack of interaction due to connectivity issues. This is an attempt to understand the problems and thereby providing solutions based on the findings.

Keywords: Online classes, Teaching-Learning Process, Students, Teachers, Online Platforms.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The world is fighting COVID-19 and a lockdown has been announced by economies around the world. Work from Home (WFH) has become the norm, particularly for service organizations. According to Government instructions, even the educational institutions had to close down momentarily, impacting the academic delivery. Therefore, education institutions needed to consider new approaches to the teaching process, and the way was the virtual classes. The pace of the disease spread, the closing of higher education institutes and the transition to online teaching were so rapid that it gave hardly any time to prepare and reflect on the possible risks or opportunities that such a sudden shift could bring. The sudden shift to online learning without any preparation particularly in nations like India where the infrastructure for online learning was not ready and the program was not planned for such a format has generated the peril that most of the pupils will become passive learners, and they seem to lose interest owing to low levels of attention span. Added to this is that the digital divide that is part of many developing nations including India, may leave a large proportion of the student population untouched.

Online education is performed in two ways either through recorded classes or through live online webinar classes. Covid-19 forced universities across India, and indeed the world, to suspend physical classrooms and move on to online classrooms. Though for most private universities in India this transaction has been smooth, the public ones are still evolving. There were also debates about the nature of education and the future of assessment and evaluation whether or not they should be done online. Although the faculties are struggling with new ways to handle this unexpected shift to online teaching, students remain hooked to their cell phones and computer screens. Online education is not as easy as talking to the microphone at one end, connecting a

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laptop or phone, and listening in at the other end. This type of education presents other problems faced by both ends of the spectrum of students and faculties. Some students who do not have sufficient internet access and/ or technology are struggling to participate in digital learning; this disparity is seen across countries. Other than this even it is noticed that learning may be stagnant as it creates a new set of passive learners that can present new challenges. Online learning is a different kind of technique and not all faculties are good at it or at least not everyone was ready for this abrupt transition from the face-to-face learning process to online learning.

2.0 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The study is carried out with the following objectives:

- ❖ To study the perception of students and teachers regarding online classes
- ❖ To analyze the benefits enjoyed by and drawbacks faced by students in attending online classes

3.0 SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The scope of the study covers students and teachers of various higher education institutions in Mangalore.

4.0 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study undertaken comprises both primary and secondary data. The primary data is first-hand information that is collected for investigation purposes. The primary information for the study was collected through a questionnaire. The structured questionnaire was distributed to students and faculties of Mangalore through Google form. Simple random sampling techniques were used for the selection of the sample. The sample size consists of 100 teachers and 100 students from different colleges in the research area. The secondary data is obtained from various journals, books, magazines and a few websites. The data were collected and recorded systematically, later analyzed by using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 20.

5.0 LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

No single work is an exception to the limitations; every work has got its limitations. Following are some of the limitations observed in the study.

- ❖ The primary data is collected through a structured questionnaire and the sample size is only limited to 200 respondents (100 teachers and 100 students).
- ❖ The perception of the respondents is limited to the period of the study.
- ❖ Time constraint.
- ❖ The study is limited to the Covid-19 pandemic lockdown period.

6.0 DATA ANALYSIS

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The demographic details of both teachers and students were collected to know their background like gender, education, etc. The following table explains the demographic background of the respondents.

Table 1: Demographic profile of the respondents (Students and Teachers)

STUDENTS				TEACHERS				
		Frequency	Percent			Frequency	Percent	
Age	16 to 20	17	17	Age	21 to 30	44	44	
	20 to 25	68	68		31 to 40	29	29	
	Above 25	15	15		41 to 50	15	15	
	Total	100	100		Above 50	12	12	
Gender	Male	50	50	Total	100	100	100	
	Female	50	50		Gender of respondents	Male	57	57
	Total	100	100			Female	43	43
Present Education	Under-Graduation	33	33	Total	100	100	100	
	Post-Graduation	47	47		Educational Qualification	Post-Graduation	74	74
	ITI/Diploma/others	20	20			Ph.D.	16	16
	Total	100	100	M.Phil		10	10	
Regularity in attending online classes	Regular	51	51	Total		100	100	100
	Almost regular	34	34		Marital Status	Married	64	64
	Sometimes	15	15			Unmarried	36	36
	Total	100	100	Total	100	100	100	
Online platform used by faculties	WhatsApp	12	12	Nature of work	Full-time	61	61	
	Zoom	37	37		Part-time	28	28	
	Skype	14	14		Visiting faculty	11	11	
	Google	3	3		Total	100	100	100

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	Classroom						
	Google Meet	34	34	Devices used	Mobile	24	24
	Total	100	100		Laptop	69	69
Device used by students	Mobile	72	72		Computer	7	7
	Laptop	24	24		Total	100	100
	Computer	4	4				
	Total	100	100				

STUDENT DATA

The study undertaken includes an equal number of respondents in gender classification where a majority of them belong to the age group of 20 to 25 years. Among the total students considered for the study majority of them pursuing their Post-Graduation in various streams.

More than 50% of total student respondents attending online classes on regular basis. A great number of respondents attend online classes by way of Zoom application. It was observed that the majority of the respondents attend online classes using mobile phones. The level of expertise in computer handling showed that the majority of the students (N=63) have a high level of computer knowledge.

TEACHER DATA

The above table shows that, among total respondents, the majority comes under the age group of 21-30 years. The majority of the teachers (74%) have a post-graduation degree only. It was observed that the majority of respondents engage in online classes through the laptop. Almost all teachers are conducting an online class for the first time due to the COVID 19 pandemic. It was found that the majority of teachers (N=49) have a moderate level of knowledge in the use of computers.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics on benefits of online classes

Benefits	N	Mean	S. D	Min.	Max.
More comfort	100	3.77	1.188	1	5
Convenience	100	3.07	1.416	1	5
Cost saving	100	3.17	1.422	1	5
Easier attendance	100	2.90	1.432	1	5
Easier access to teachers	100	2.69	1.433	1	5
Allows for self-placed learning	100	2.72	1.280	1	5

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The descriptive statistics for the various benefits gained by students through online classes are shown in Table 2. The result displayed mean ratings of benefits of online classes in the range of 2.72 to 3.77 with the standard deviation between 1.433 to 1.188.

Out of the above-mentioned benefits of an online class, students rate highest for more comfort with a mean value of 3.77 and standard deviation of 1.188 followed by cost saving with a mean value of 3.17 and standard deviation of 1.422.

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics Difficulties faced by students during online classes

Difficulties	N	Mean	S. D	Min.	Max.
Technical issues	100	3.07	1.465	1	5
Adaptability struggle	100	3.42	1.350	1	5
Time management	100	3.09	1.518	1	5
Lack of self-motivation	100	3.16	1.376	1	5
Lack of technical resources or proficiency	100	3.63	1.169	1	5

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The descriptive statistics for the difficulties faced by students in online classes are shown in Table 3. The result disclosed mean ratings of difficulties in online classes in the range of 3.07 to 3.63 with the standard deviation between 1.518 to 1.169.

Out of the above-mentioned problems in an online class, students rate highest for lack of technical proficiency with a mean value of 3.77 and standard deviation of 1.169 followed by adaptability struggle with a mean value of 3.42 and standard deviation of 1.350.

6.1 STUDENTS DATA

HYPOTHESIS:

H₀: There is no significant difference between a demographical variable with respect to various benefits gained and difficulties faced in online classes.

H₁: There is a significant difference between a demographical variable with respect to various benefits gained and difficulties faced in online classes.

Table 4: Kruskal-Wallis test values and Mann-Whitney test value and their significance between various demographical variables

Benefits	Demographical Variable		
	Age (Chi-Square value)	Gender (Z value)	Education (Chi-Square value)
More comfort	0.239 >0.05 H ₀ is Accepted NS	0.307 >0.05 H ₀ is Accepted NS	1.179 >0.05 H ₀ is Accepted NS
Convenience	4.997 <0.05* H₁ is Accepted S	0.624 >0.05 H ₀ is Accepted NS	4.738 <0.05* H₁ is Accepted S

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Cost Saving	0.518 >0.05 H ₀ is Accepted NS	0.349 >0.05 H ₀ is Accepted NS	3.659 <0.05* H₁ is Accepted S
Easier attendance	0.341 >0.05 H ₀ is Accepted NS	0.567 >0.05 H ₀ is Accepted NS	1.570 >0.05 H ₀ is Accepted NS
Easier access to teachers	0.048 >0.05 H ₀ is Accepted NS	0.053 >0.05 H ₀ is Accepted NS	0.113 >0.05 H ₀ is Accepted NS
Allows self-placed learning	1.361 >0.05 H ₀ is Accepted NS	0.778 >0.05 H ₀ is Accepted NS	1.262 >0.05 H ₀ is Accepted NS
Difficulties			
Technical issues	0.341 >0.05 H ₀ is Accepted NS	1.011 >0.05 H ₀ is Accepted NS	1.273 >0.05 H ₀ is Accepted NS
Adaptability struggle	0.352 >0.05 H ₀ is Accepted NS	0.152 >0.05 H ₀ is Accepted NS	2.533 >0.05 H ₀ is Accepted NS
Time management	3.183 >0.05 H ₀ is Accepted NS	1.010 >0.05 H ₀ is Accepted NS	0.017 >0.05 H ₀ is Accepted NS
Lac of self-motivation	0.339 >0.05 H ₀ is Accepted NS	0.007 >0.05 H ₀ is Accepted NS	0.024 >0.05 H ₀ is Accepted NS
Lack of technical resources/ proficiency	0.280 >0.05 H ₀ is Accepted NS	1.777 >0.05 H ₀ is Accepted NS	0.376 >0.05 H ₀ is Accepted NS

**Significance at 1% level * Significance at 5% level

The K-W test has been used to know the significant difference between age and education with reference to benefits enjoyed by students in attending online classes. There is a significance association between different age groups and education levels with respect to convenience in attending online classes with p value less than 0.05.

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Based on the Mann-Whitney U test value, there is no significant difference between benefits enjoyed by students in online classes with regard to gender as p value is more than 0.05

6.2 TEACHERS

HYPOTHESIS:

H₀: There is no significant association between age, gender and devices used with respect to comfortability in engaging online classes, meeting individual needs, student’s participation in online classes and interaction of students in online classes.

H₁: There is a significance association between age, gender and devices used with respect to comfortability in engaging online classes, meeting individual needs, student’s participation in online classes and interaction of students in online classes.

Variable	Age	Gender	Devices Used
Comfortability in engaging online classes	FETV: 35.384 P=.000 P<0.05 H1 is accepted	CSTV: 2.458 >0.05 H ₀ is Accepted NS	CSTV: 5.493 >0.05 H ₀ is Accepted NS
interaction of students in online classes	FETV: 5.414 >0.05 H ₀ is Accepted NS	CSTV: 1.209 >0.05 H ₀ is Accepted NS	CSTV: 2.474 >0.05 H ₀ is Accepted NS
online assignments	FETV: 2.158 >0.05 H ₀ is Accepted NS	CSTV: 11.111 >0.05 H ₁ is Accepted NS	CSTV: 2.951 >0.05 H ₀ is Accepted NS
Meeting individual needs in online classes	FETV: 8.449 >0.05 H ₀ is Accepted NS	CSTV: 1.283 >0.05 H ₀ is Accepted NS	CSTV: 3.330 >0.05 H ₀ is Accepted NS
Rating student’s participation in online	FETV: 2.678 >0.05	CSTV: 2.325 >0.05	CSTV: 4.285 >0.05

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classes	H ₀ is Accepted NS	H ₀ is Accepted NS	H ₀ is Accepted NS
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There is no significant difference between age, gender and devices used with regard to other variables considered for the test. There is no major difference identified.

7.0 DISCUSSION

The focus of this paper was to examine the perceptions of students and teachers about online classes during the Pandemic. Many previous studies have found that the satisfaction of face-to-face learning is greater than that of online learning, and this study has also found that face-to-face learning is more desirable than online classes.

Students believed that an online class have a great influence on their learning style (N=61), and they also acknowledged that they receive help from teachers in online class such as having study material and clarifying their doubt through online resources as well. But students do not believe that an online class replaces the traditional face-to-face classroom teaching, and they feel that even though online classes are comfortable but it’s less compared to the conventional teaching process. This is because online classes are in its infancy in an educational institution.

In the study even though it was observed that students are quite benefited from online classes there are students who were facing difficulties in accessing online classes. It was evident from the study. Most of the teachers adopted online teaching for the first time during the Covid pandemic. This has changed the conventional education system followed so far in India. Teachers learned to use technology to aid in the teaching-learning process. Many students opined that online teaching will become a part and parcel of higher education in days to come.

8.0 SUGGESTIONS

Following are some of the suggestions based on the findings of the study

- ❖ Before adopting online teaching in educational institutions prior training should be given to both faculties and students.
- ❖ Teachers should engage with students online from time to time posting academic activities that encourage students to participate themselves in it.
- ❖ Teachers should try to create a supportive learning environment for their students through teacher-to-student engagement and student-to-student interaction.
- ❖ Providing feedback about the students during online class will promote student’s engagement in the class.

9.0 CONCLUSION

Due to COVID-19 all schools and colleges shut down for an uncertain time period. Adapting online classes has become the need for the day and even the Government and UGC also suggested to higher education institutions to undertake online classes for students by means they can finish their syllabus on time and plan for semester-end exams. This study tries to understand the point of views of teachers and students about the online teaching-learning process and it was noticed that many students are facing problems like technical issues, lack of availability of technical resources and proficiency and even faculties also facing issues as they exposed to the kind of atmosphere where they did not have any practice which made both the end to struggle a

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lot. Even though there were challenges in front of both the spectrum they managed to deal with this and it was suggested to introduce few more measures in the system to make e-learning more effective in future days.

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